

Development Of A Problem-Based Learning Model With Character On The Theme Of Social Cultural Diversity For Improving Creative Thinking Ability In Elementary School Students

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 26, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 28, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Problem-Based Learning Model, Character Education, Creative Thinking, Socio-Cultural Diversity, Thematic Learning.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6773092</p>	<p><i>Development research related to learning models, methods and designs, and development research that products of teaching materials in the form of modules, media and evaluation instruments often ignores the essence and substance of the 2013 curriculum which emphasizes the importance of character building in elementary school students. Starting from this trend, development research on the theme of Socio-Cultural Diversity chose the Development of a Character-Based Problem-Based Learning Model. The choice of the theme is intended so that the learning model applied to the learning process in elementary schools can foster creativity and problem solving skills scientifically and aspects of character bulding. In particular, the purpose of this research is to produce a problem-based learning model product containing valid and effective characters to improve creative thinking skills and learning outcomes. The development model used is the Plomp development model. The research subjects were public and private elementary school students in Pematangsiantar City and Simalungun Regency, North Sumatra, Indonesia. The students who became the research sample were divided into 3 control class and 3 experimental class with a total sample of 90 students. The instruments used in this study were structured and open questionnaires, observation rubrics and questionnaires. The data collected was analyzed by combining descriptive statistical research aproach and qualitative models. The results of the study (1) learning tools that include modules, teacher books, student books, learning implementation plans and Student Worksheets (2) the product of the problem-based learning model device with character content developed was assessed by the validator as valid with a score of 3.76; the validity of the material aspects is 3.78, the language aspect is 3.88, the design and media aspects are 3.75. (3) From the results of trials in small and medium groups, the modules developed are proven to increase creativity with achievement. 76.08 and the medium group 78.43. The level of effectiveness of the module developed in the large group based on the paired sample test was achieved as low as 65, the highest score 80 and an average of 76.15 indicating that there were differences in student learning outcomes at the pretest and posttest, both in the control sample and the experimental sample.</i></p>

Introduction

21st century education is an educational system that seeks to meet all the needs of humans living in that century. Abidin, Y (2015) stated that 21st century education aims to create people who are critical in intellectual, creative in thinking, ethical in relationships, and have character in life. 21st century education according to Bialik, M.; Fadel, C.; Trilling, B.; Nilsson, P.; Groff, J (2015) must fulfill four components, namely knowledge, skills, character, and metacognition. 21st century learning requires technology mastery skills through information literacy, media and technological literacy.

Frydenberg and Andone, (2011) identify the competencies needed in the 21st century including abilities (1) life and career skills (flexible and adaptive, initiative and independent, social and cultural skills, productive and accountable, leadership and responsibility); (2) learning and innovation skills (creative and innovation, problem solving critical thinking, communication and collaboration; and (3) skills in technology, information, communication and computerization. These three skills are summarized in a scheme called the rainbow of century knowledge skills 21 (Triling and Fadel, 2009).

In the American Association of School Librarians it is stated that learning in the 21st century has a new dimension with the exponential expansion of information, ever-changing tools, digital texts, demands that continue to increase and change very quickly. The exponential development of information requires

multiplication of critical thinking, creative, communication skills, problem-solving skills, the ability to work together, develop skills, attitudes, and high responsibility. Students in this era are also required to access and utilize information in order to foster the spirit of innovation, create new knowledge and social problems that are developing very quickly.

According to the results of the World Innovation Summit for Education (2022) survey, regarding school projections in 2030, 93 % of education experts surveyed stated that they support schools that apply innovative methods and use new teaching approaches and creative processes. The future learning model has conceptually been designed and implemented in the 2013 primary, secondary and vocational education curriculum in Indonesia called Curriculum 2013 or K13. The achievement of the noble goals of developing K13 is determined by the participation of stakeholders including educators, students, staff education units, education unit managers, education service officers, monitoring teams, supervisors, education observers and the public.

The implementation of the 2013 Curriculum at various types and levels of education in Indonesia is intended to produce Indonesian people who are productive, creative, innovative, and affective through strengthening integrated attitudes (know why), skills (know how), and knowledge (know what). In learning activities, strengthening the three domains of competence mandated in K13 is realized by encouraging students to be active and creative in observing, asking questions, reasoning, inferring and communicating (verbally and in writing) in every learning process and activity. Through the development of the 2013 curriculum, it is hoped that students will have much better attitudes, skills, and knowledge competencies.

Through the development and implementation of K-13, every educator is expected to be able to realize a rainbow of 21st century knowledge skills and character optimally by mainstreaming the application of the Higher Order Thinking Skills learning model, abbreviated as HOTS, innovative, creative and sustainable. Optimizing the application of the Higher Order Thinking Skills learning model, in line with the characteristics of Generation Z, one of the characteristics of Hyper-Costumation is that they have a very fluid life towards something, they cannot be restrained from doing what they want (Stillman, 2018). Mainstreaming the HOTS aspect is intended so that students have a rainbow of 21st century knowledge skills which include (1) the ability to innovate and develop creativity (2) problem solving and critical thinking skills and (3) communication and collaboration skills. These three forms of learning outcomes will grow in students if they are trained, accustomed from childhood to explore, inquiry, discover and solve problems. Opinions Cahyaningsih, U., & Ghufron, A (2016) and Subekti (2014). Through the mainstreaming of HOTS, it is also expected that students have life skills such as flexibility, leadership, initiative, productivity and the ability to interact with people.

Center for Global Education (2018), recommends every educational institution to design learning that is able to lead students to have "The Four Domains of Global Competence" which consists of 4Cs, namely: Critical Thinking, Creative Thinking, Collaboration, and Communication). Through the Four Domains of Global Competence, students are expected to: (1) have a great curiosity about the surrounding environment and the global world; (2) able to recognize and detect opportunities; (3) able to communicate ideas; and (4) able to make decisions and take necessary actions.

The Four Domains of Global Competence is very much needed in the 21st century, because the phenomena and life of this century are marked by disruption and uncertainty. From The Four Domains of Global Competence, the choice of study is related to creative thinking skills. Through the ability to think creatively, problem solving skills, enable each individual to (1) actualize himself optimally, (2) take advantage of various opportunities for a better quality of life, (3) solve problems systematically and critically, (4) generate pride and intellectual satisfaction. individually as well as socially (Awang and Ramli (2008: 19), Munandar (2009: 31).

The development and implementation of K-13 is not only intended to create a rainbow of 21st century knowledge skills and The Four Domains of Global Competence is also aimed at developing the nation's character, character and civilization. Subagia and Wiratma, (2012) state that the implementation of K-13 is an optimization of the potential development and basic elements of students including the ability to act, speaking ability, and thinking ability. These three abilities are called Triakaya. Mainstreaming character building in K-13 is the implementation of national education goals that develop all potential learners, namely cognitive, psychomotor and skill aspects. The achievement of the three aspects of the potential of students is expressly formulated in the goals of national education, namely developing people who believe and fear God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic and responsible citizens.

The formulation of the national education goals emphasizes that educational institutions at various levels are the spearhead of the formation of the character of students. Therefore, since the commemoration of the national education day on May 2, 2011, the Government has launched the National Movement for Character Education (2010-2025). This movement was then intensified by the Presidential Regulation no. 87 of 2017, concerning Strengthening Character Education (PPK) and Permendiknas No. 20 of 2018 concerning Strengthening Character Education (PPK), namely: religious, nationalist, integrity, mutual cooperation and independence. Strengthening Character Education is an educational movement in schools to strengthen the

character of students through harmonization of the heart (ethics), taste (aesthetics), thought (literacy), and sports (kinesthetic) with support involving the public and cooperation between schools, family, and society. The five main character values by the Curriculum Center of the Research and Development Agency of the Ministry of National Education and Culture are described in 18 aspects, namely: religious, honest, tolerance, discipline, hard work, creative, independent, democratic, curiosity, national spirit, love for the homeland, appreciate achievement, friendly, love peace, love to read, care for the environment, care about social, and responsibility.

Lickona, Schaps, and Lewis. (2007) identify the characters that need to be nurtured in students on the moral knowing, moral feeling and moral action. Moral knowing includes moral awareness, understanding the moral values, taking perspectives, moral reasons, decision and self-knowledge. Moral feeling consists of conscience, self-esteem, empathy, loving kindness, control yourself and humility and moral action includes competency, wants and habit.

Although the national education goals are directed at developing all the potential of students, namely the cognitive, psychomotor and skill aspects in a balanced way, in reality the empirical learning model applied in the teaching and learning process rests and is directed solely at the achievement of the cognitive dimension. Three learning models that are emphasized in K-13 namely Problem Based Learning, Project Based Learning, Model Discovery and Inquiry are oriented solely to improve the cognitive and creative abilities of students. For example, research on the use of problem-based learning models was carried out by Siagian, Saragih and Sinaga (2019), Jamal, Ibrahim, Abdul Halim, Dayana, Surif, and Osman, Sharifah, (2020), Octafianellis; Sudarmin; Panca, (2021), Oktavia, Z., & Ridlo, S. (2020), Capraro, Morgan, Slough, (2013) and Handoyo, Rosbiono, Sopandi (2021), Birgili, B. (2015). From the results of this study, it is known that the use of problem-based learning models can improve students' meta-cognitive abilities and increase creative thinking. This is in line with the view of Arends (2008: 41) that problem-based learning serves as a springboard for information investigation and investigation.

The research on the use of the Problem-Based Learning model was conducted against the background of concerns and conditions of the conventional teacher teaching model Vera et al., (2019) and the low creativity of students (Wulandari, Mawardi and Wardani, 2019) and Mashitoh, Sukestiyarno, Wardono, (2021).

The mainstreaming of the Problem-Based Learning model for improving students' creative skills is of course very positive, it needs to be echoed because it is needed in the face of the era of disruption. It's just that in the era of disruption marked by discontent, it requires other skills, namely life skills such as flexibility, leadership, initiative, productive and interacting. Life skills are basically a character rooted in the individual's personality that functions like a "machine" to encourage how to act, behave, and respond to behavior, phenomena and a dynamically developing social environment.

Therefore, Koesoema (2007) views character as a dynamic condition of the individual's anthropological structure, which is not just a natural determination, but a life effort to become more and more integral overcoming the natural determination within himself for the process of continuous self-improvement. It is the freedom of man that makes the anthropological structure not subject to the laws of nature, but rather becomes a factor that helps integral human development. The same thing was stated by Ardianto (2011) which defines character as a series of attitudes to do the best, intellectual capacity, critical thinking and moral integrity (honest and responsible), maintaining moral principles in situations full of injustice, interpersonal and emotional skills that allow a person to interact effectively in a variety of circumstances, and a commitment to contribute to the community and society.

According to Soedarsono (2008), character is dynamic, its development is influenced by individual dimensions, the process of interaction, education and learning. In this connection, Erfan (2011) states that character education is not only teaching what is right and what is wrong, but instilling good habits in students to understand which actions are right and which are wrong and students enjoy good deeds and carry them out in their lives daily. The results of this process produce a way of thinking and behaving that characterizes each individual to live and work together, both in the family, community, nation and state environment, Suyanto (2009). So that character can be interpreted as a way of thinking and behaving that is unique to each individual to live and work together, both within the family, community, and nation and state (Samani, 2011:41).

The descriptions of the characters in the three paragraphs above illustrate that descriptions, analysis and character education tend to be general in nature and studies that analyze character development associated with the use of problem-based learning models can be said to be still limited, among others carried out by Puspoko Jati, Ismanto, Sulasmono; Bambang (2019), Baharun, and Ummah, (2018), Wardani, Sriwarthini, Rahmatih; Nikmah; Sadia (2019). The use of problem-based learning models as mentioned above is related to increasing students' creativity and criticality, Tiwari, Lai, Yuen, (2006). Studies on the use of Problem-Based Learning Models related to the fields of Social Sciences and the arts are very limited, among others by Susanto, R., & Suryadarma, I. G. P. (2019) and Ulger, (2018).

Starting from this empirical reality, this paper reveals the use of problem-based learning models containing character in thematic learning of Social Science material on the theme of social diversity in basic education. The choice of research topic is based on the following reasons: first, at the macro level, the ability to

think creatively is a national problem. This is shown from the various products consumed by the Indonesian people, most of which are imported products rather than domestic products, due to the low engineering and innovation capabilities of domestic industry and technology. The lack of creativity, engineering ability and industrial and technological innovation has resulted in the fulfillment of daily needs, such as salt making, which does not require high technology, to be met through imports.

Second, in the field of education, the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) ranking from the results of the 2018 PISA test, Indonesia is in the 70s out of 78 countries. Third, at the micro level in elementary school education units as reported by Vera, Mawardi and Astuti, S. (2019), the creativity of elementary school students is low. Based on the research of Wulandari, Mawardi, Wardani, (2019), this condition is due to the fact that most teachers are less concerned about increasing student creativity, limited understanding and ability of teachers to use approaches and learning models that stimulate creativity and Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) such as the Based Learning Model. Problems, discovery and inquiry models in learning. Teaching and learning activities tend to be mechanistic, routine and limited in the use of relevant and modern learning media (Mashitoh, Sukestiyarno and Wardono, 2021).

From the identification of the macro and micro scale problems, the research problems are formulated as follows: (1) how is the problem-based learning model product with character content that can improve the creative thinking ability of students at the elementary school level? (2) What is the level of validity of the problem-based learning model product with character content that can improve students' creative thinking skills at the elementary school level? (3) how is the effectiveness of the problem-based learning model product containing character that can improve the creative thinking ability of students at the elementary school level?

II. METHOD

This research approach is categorized as research and development which refers to development research developed by Plomp (2010:13), Kuffman (2009:67). According to Plomp, development research is a systematic study of the process of designing, developing and evaluating "interventions" (programs, teaching and learning strategies and their devices, products and systems) as solutions to complex problems in practical education. According to Plomp's view, the research and development steps consist of five phases, namely (1) initial investigation phase, (2) design phase, (3) realization phase, (4) test, evaluation, and revision phase, and (5) implementation phase.

This research was conducted in elementary schools in Pematangsiantar City and Simalungun Regency. The selection of this location is based on the consideration that the quality of basic education is quite diverse, there are categories of very good, moderate and poor. Likewise, the quality of human resources and educational infrastructure in the two regions varies widely.

The instruments used in this study were: (1) a closed questionnaire validation sheet, (2) a questionnaire about the implementation and effectiveness of the model (3) a questionnaire about student creativity, (4) an observation rubric about student character and (5) a questionnaire about the results. learning outcomes. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistical models and qualitative analysis approaches.

The criteria for the validity of the problem-based learning model product with character values are 80 or > 80. This score is also used as a basis for measuring the effectiveness of the developed model product, namely the Problem-Based Learning Model with Character-Based Problems in learning the field of Social Sciences in Elementary Schools. Operationally, the criteria for the effectiveness of the product model developed are: (1) classical student learning completeness, namely at least 70% of students who take part in learning are able to achieve a minimum average score of more than 75 for learning outcomes tests (maximum score 100) and (2) At least 75% of the many subjects studied (for each trial) gave a positive response to the components and learning activities

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Research Results

3.1.2. Preliminary Investigation

The results of observations of the conditions of students and teachers during the implementation of learning in the classroom, it can be concluded that: (1) teachers do not understand the importance of using problem-based learning models that contain character, (2) , (2) in learning activities most students tend to be passive, the learning model is still teacher-centered, (3) the intellectual potential and creative thinking abilities of students have not developed optimally; (4) The design and implementation of learning activities carried out by teachers tend to be conventional.

The general conclusion from the results of the initial survey is that the learning process that takes place in the study rooms has not paid attention to the aspects of creativity and the needs of students' active activities. Based on searching and extracting information from the field, there has been no systematic and programmed effort from teachers in the field of Social Sciences to develop creative thinking skills and character. Documents of learning tools owned by teachers, such as learning implementation plans, teacher books, student books,

instruments or evaluation sheets of student learning outcomes, tend to be separate and difficult to develop creative thinking skills, solve real social problems faced by students in everyday life.

3.1.2. Design

The design for developing a problem-based learning model with character in research refers to the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation No. 65 of 2013 concerning Standards for Primary and Secondary Education Processes, components of the Learning Implementation Plan (RPP). In Permendikbud No. 65 of 2013 the components of the Learning Implementation Plan (RPP include: Identity, Core Competencies, Basic Competencies, Competency Achievement Indicators, Learning Objectives, Teaching Materials, Time Allocation, Learning Methods, Steps for Learning Activities, Characteristics of expected students, Assessment of learning outcomes, and learning resources.

Learning design starts from what students already know in accordance with the context and only continues in a wider context. Learning designs are arranged oriented to the development of science and technology, and the values of today's life, so that learning activities can facilitate students to learn independently. The learning process is designed to be student-centered to encourage motivation, interest, creativity, initiative, inspiration, independence, and enthusiasm for learning, using a scientific approach that is in accordance with the 2013 curriculum. A learning process that makes the surrounding environment a source of learning.

In accordance with Permendikbud No. 65 of 2013, the preparation of learning device designs is oriented to the development of science and technology, social practices and the values of life that live in society. The learning design developed provides opportunities and space for the creation of a climate of effective learning activities and can facilitate students to learn independently. The learning process is designed to be student-centered to generate motivation, interest, creativity, initiative, inspiration, independence, and enthusiasm for student learning. The approach used in preparing the learning design is a scientific approach in accordance with the 2013 curriculum.

The learning design developed as far as possible has linkages and integration between competencies and/or between the components of the Learning Implementation Plan (RPP) and learning tools by taking into account the linkages and integration between KI, KD, competency achievement indicators, learning materials, learning activities, assessments, and Learning Resources. The Learning Implementation Design (RPP) and learning tools are based on thematic learning which is characterized by integration across subjects, across learning aspects, and cultural diversity. The design of the Learning Implementation Plan (RPP) and learning tools considers the application of information and communication technology in an integrated, systematic, and effective manner according to the situation and conditions of the school location and the socio-cultural psychology background of the students.

3.1.3. Realization

In this phase, an initial script of learning tools is produced which is adapted to the Character-Based Problem Based Learning model. Learning tools consist of Syllabus, Learning Implementation Plan (RPP), Teacher Book Design, Student Book Design, Student Worksheet (LKPD), Evaluation Instrument. One of the characteristics of this research activity is the modification and innovation of processes, procedures and activities in the application of a charged problem-based learning model in the thematic learning of science on Socio-Cultural Diversity at the elementary school level.

At the realization stage of the Learning Implementation Plan that is prepared to have linkages and integration between competencies (between Core Competencies, Basic Competencies, Learning Objectives and indicators); integration between competency achievement with learning materials and resources, integration between competency achievement with learning activities and integration between competency and assessment.

Given that in K-13 the learning model in elementary schools is thematic, the Learning Implementation Plan (RPP) that is prepared accommodates integration across fields of study (Natural Science, Social Sciences and Language), integration between cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains and considers background intellectual level, psychology and socio-cultural background of students. Modifications and innovations of the Character-Based Problem-Based Learning Model developed in the Learning Implementation Design (RPP) on the Socio-Cultural Diversity Theme are presented in Table 1.

Tabel 1. Stages of Character-Based Problem Based Learning Socio-Cultural Diversity Theme

Stages of Problem Based Learning	Socio-Cultural Diversity Theme	
	Character	Creative Thinking Ability
Orientation	Concern	Smoothness, Authenticity
Organizing students to study	Responsibility, Creative and hard work.	Elaboration

Guiding research	Creative and hard work, Responsibility	Elaboration, fluency
Develop and present work	Honesty, Creative and hard work, Responsibility, caring	Smoothness, authenticity, flexibility
Analyze and evaluate work	Honesty, Responsibility	Fluency,Authenticity, Elaboration

In the table above, it can be seen that at each stage of learning based on the Design Problem-Based Learning Model, the achievement of competency aspects of character and creative abilities is included. In the Learning Implementation Plan on Socio-Cultural Diversity material, the achievement of competence is carried out through a series of independent learning activities, collaboration, providing feedback, enrichment and reinforcement, enrichment and remedial.

3.1.4. Product Validity of Character-Based Problem-Based Learning Models

The instrument validity of the model used consisted of n instruments to measure the validity of the material, a learning design validity instrument and a language validity instrument. After the instrument was compiled, an analysis was carried out by a team of experts. There were three expert involved to measure the validity of each instrument. The results of the expert team's analysis on the three aspects of the instrument are presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Validation of the Character-loaded Problem Learning Model

Based on the data processing results from the validation of the Character-Based Problem-Based Learning model conducted by 9 experts consisting of 3 material experts, 3 learning design experts and 3 language experts. In the early stages of the learning model developed in the design aspect, the average value for each validation activity was still below 3.5. If referring to the criteria determined in the research, the level of validity of the Problem-Based Learning model developed is not considered valid.

Based on input and suggestions from each validator, revisions were made to improve the model book, such as adding supporting theories related to the constructivism model, scientific approach or problem based learning approach. In the next revision, a study of the developed model includes the instructional impact and the driving impact of the developed model. So that the Problem-Based Learning Model Loaded with Character developed has met the criteria of validity and has a solid theoretical basis and there is consistency between the components of the model internally in an integrated manner.

The results of the validation of the validator aspects of the language, in stage 1 obtained a score below 3.5. Referring to the validity criteria, it can be stated that the Character-Based Problem Based Model module still needs to be improved. Suggestions for improvement from the validator are improving sentences to make them more communicative and easy to understand, connectedness between words/phrases, paragraphs, and between chapters, improvement of the language used such as Let's Find Out, Let's Discuss, Let's Be Creative, Let's Conclude. After making improvements, at the 3rd validation stage the language aspect obtained an average score above 3.5 which was declared valid and could be used for the next stage.

Gambar 2. Validation of Learning Devices with Problem Learning Model

Based on the results of the validation of the Character-Based Problem Based Learning Model device which was carried out by 3 material field validators, in the first stage the average value was below 3.5. If referring to the criteria determined in this study, the validity of the Problem-Based Model with Character Content in the material field has not been categorized as valid. Therefore, it is necessary to make improvements to the content, completeness of learning tools including answers and answer keys.

In the improvement of learning device materials there are additions and improvements. Suggestions for improvement in learning tools in the field of material include, among others, in the field of Social Sciences regarding interactions between humans and human interactions with the surrounding environment; text on healthy food and protection of trees and plants for the field of Natural Sciences. After making improvements, at the 3rd validation stage in the field of learning device materials, an average value above 3.5 is declared valid. Based on these results, the material for the Problem-Based Model Learning Tool contains Characters is declared valid and can be used for the next test stage.

For learning tools in the form of Student Worksheets (LKPD) after being declared valid by the validator, followed by a limited trial to determine the reliability and sensitivity. The results of the characteristic test of the Student Worksheet (LKPD) items are presented in Table 2.

Tabel2. Test the Characteristics of Learning Outcome Test Items
Correlations

		SOAL1	SOAL2	SOAL3	SOAL4	SOAL5	SOAL6
SOAL1	Pearson Correlation	1	.770**	.556*	.640**	.530*	.456*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.011	.002	.016	.043
	N	20	20	20	20	20	20
SOAL2	Pearson Correlation	.770**	1	.771**	.782**	.677**	.657**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.001	.002
	N	20	20	20	20	20	20
SOAL3	Pearson Correlation	.556*	.771**	1	.918**	.625**	.699**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.011	.000		.000	.003	.001
	N	20	20	20	20	20	20
SOAL4	Pearson Correlation	.640**	.782**	.918**	1	.752**	.753**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	20	20	20	20	20	20
SOAL5	Pearson Correlation	.530*	.677**	.625**	.752**	1	.849**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.016	.001	.003	.000		.000

	N	20	20	20	20	20	20
SOAL6	Pearson Correlation	.456*	.657**	.699**	.753**	.849**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.043	.002	.001	.000	.000	
	N	20	20	20	20	20	20

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.923	.932	6

Table 2 shows the results of the test reliability calculation with reliability coefficient = 0.932. Value = 0.932, if it refers to the reliability criteria set in the study, it can be concluded that the test instrument compiled has a high degree of reliability. The value of r for each test item against the validity criteria, it can be concluded that the test item has a high and sufficient degree of validity.

3.1.5. Product Effectiveness of Character-Based Problem-Based Learning Model

The effectiveness of the product model developed is proven from the results of the small, medium and large group trials that are the samples of this study. The results of the trials in the three groups are presented in this section. The data on the results of trial-1 and trial-2 for the Student Creativity test with a research sample of 20 students are shown in the following figure.

Figure 3. The Value of Student Creativity in Trial-I

Based on the data from Figure 3, it is known that the value of students' creative thinking abilities in the 1st trial is 73.95, standard deviation is 4.476, and completeness is 55%. The value of students' creative thinking abilities, if it refers to the criteria for the level of creativity according to the provisions, it is concluded that the level of creativity of students is at the "medium" level. Meanwhile, in terms of student learning completeness in the first stage of the trial, it was stated that they did not meet the requirements for the effectiveness of achieving learning objectives, it was necessary to conduct a II-trial.

Figure 4 The Value of Student Creativity in Trial-II

The value of the trial stage-2 obtained a score of 77.33, standard deviation of 2,592, and learning completeness of 85%. The acquisition of test scores-2, if it refers to the criteria for the level of creativity

according to the standard, it is stated that the level of creativity of students is at a "high" level. Where the completeness of student learning is 85% in the phase-2 trial which has met the requirements for the effectiveness of achieving learning objectives. Student learning outcomes are determined by the average results of the evaluations carried out in each section, namely the Indonesian language aspect, the science aspect, and the social studies aspect. Student learning outcomes using learning models and tools can be seen in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5 Student Learning Outcomes in Test-I

After students study each section in the developed textbook, students are given assignments which are then graded. The results of the assessment are then averaged for each trial. The average value of student learning outcomes as shown in Figure 5 at the time of trial-1, the average value is 74.58, standard deviation is 4,549 with learning completeness of 55%. This data shows that the trials carried out have not met the specified requirements. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct trial-2 to improve the weaknesses in the learning process in trial-1.

Figure 4.5 Student Learning Outcomes in Trial-II

In Figure 4.5, it is known that the average value of the class is 78,433, the standard deviation is 3,061 with learning completeness of 90%. Based on this value, it was concluded that the 2nd trial was declared to have fulfilled the learning mastery requirements.

The validity of the Character-Based Problem-Based Learning Model developed in this study was equipped with teacher response data, as a form of practicality test for the developed model. The teacher responses from the four elementary schools studied came from teachers on duty in Simalungun district and Pematang Siantar City in general gave a positive response to the Character-Based Problem-Based Learning Model. The positive response delivered by the teacher is in the form of their statements containing a feeling and attitude of being happy, interesting, motivated and interested in applying models and tools in learning activities. Data on teacher responses to learning components and activities came from six class and field teachers.

Table 3 The Average Value of Teacher Responses in Trial I

Rated aspect	Response Phase I		Response Phase II	
	f	%	F	%
Attractiveness	4.25	70.83	5.00	83.33
Novelty	4.75	79.17	5.25	87.50
Interest in sustainability	4.00	66.67	4.75	79.17

Average Teacher Response	4.33	72.22	5.00	83.33
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Based on the results of data analysis from table 3, it is known that overall, the teacher's response in the first trial to learning tools, learning models, and creative thinking ability tests was 72.22%. The teacher's response data in I to learning tools, learning models, and creative thinking ability tests still do not meet the practical requirements. After receiving input from the teachers at stage 1, then all components of the learning device were repaired and their responses were asked. It turned out that the response delivered by the teachers to learning tools, learning models, and creative thinking ability tests increased to 83.33%. This value describes the level of practicality of the learning tools, learning models, and the results of the creative thinking ability test developed.

3.1.6. The Effectiveness of Character-Based Problem-Based Learning Models at the Implementation Stage

At the implementation stage, a trial of the Problem-Based Learning Model with Characters was carried out in two groups which were the research sample, namely the control group and the experimental group. Based on data from the control group and the experimental group, which were tested and analyzed using the Paired sample test, the results are presented in table 4.

Table 4 Test Results Paired Sample Test

Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 Pretest Control	73.2658	40	1.50253	.23757
Posttest Control	75.6575	40	2.56521	.40560
Pair 2 PretestExperiment	71.1338	40	3.68312	.58235
PosttestExperiment	75.5922	40	3.39097	.53616

Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences				T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower				Upper
Pair 1	PretestControl- PosttestControl	-2.39175	2.06870	.32709	-3.05335	-1.73015	-7.312	39	.000
Pair 2	PretestExperime nt - PosttestExperime nt	-4.45850	3.72085	.58832	-5.64849	-3.26851	-7.578	39	.000

Based on the results of the paired test, it was concluded that there was a difference in the average student learning outcomes between the pretest and posttest scores between the control class and the experimental class. The significance value in pair 1 and pair 2 is $0.000 < 0.05$. This means that the problem-based learning model with character has a significant impact on increasing students' creative thinking skills and learning outcomes.

3.2. Discussion

From the exposure and data analysis of the validity, effectiveness and practicality of the developed model, referring to Nieveen (1999:127-128), the Character-Based Problem-Based Learning Model that was developed belongs to the category of valid learning model. Character-Based Problem Based Learning Models that are valid, effective and practical are needed in thematic learning on social science material in elementary schools. The validity and effectiveness of the application of the developed model is in line with the results of the research by Ambarita (2019). The Character-Based Problem-Based Learning Model resulting from the research strengthens the views expressed by Krathwohl (2002), Anderson & Krathwohl (2001), namely to increase factual, conceptual knowledge, procedural, and metacognitive, creative and critical thinking.

The creative thinking skills studied from the Application of Problem-Based Learning Model Loaded with Character are fluency of thinking, flexibility, elaboration and originality developed by Guilford and the character proposed by Lickona (1991), namely caring, responsibility, creativity, hard work and honesty. The validity and effectiveness of the application of the Character-Based Problem Based Learning Model on the theme of Socio-Cultural Diversity is relevant with the results of research conducted by Yoon, Woo, Treagust, and Chandrasegaran, (2014), González, R., & Batanero, F. (2016) in the field of science and engineering;

Ulger, (2018), in arts education; Dondlinger, M. J. and J. K. McLeod, 2015 in the field of training and games; Ersoy, E., & Baser, (2014), Tiwari, Lai, Yuen, (2006), Susanto, R., & Suryadarma, I. G. P. (2019) and Hidayah, R., Fajaroh, F., Parlan, P., & Dasna, I. W. (2021) in the field of social humanities and education.

In the era of disruption and The Four Domains of Global Competence, learning achievement of creative, critical and metacognitive thinking skills alone is seen as insufficient. In an era of disruption characterized by uncertainty, students need additional skills in the form of life skills and character. In human life, life skills or characters act as "engines" that encourage a person to act, behave, and respond to behavior, phenomena and the social environment that is developing very quickly.

In line with the demands of the era of disruption and The Four Domains of Global Competence, the application of superior learning models such as problem-based learning models, project models, discovery and inquiry need to be developed, modified and innovated continuously. In this study, the innovation of the problem-based learning model with character was chosen. Additional character-laden words are the keywords of this development research. The addition and integration of characters in the problem-based learning model has implications for changes in steps, procedures, materials and forms of learning evaluation.

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The form of the study and integration of problem-based learning models, from the author's search, is a new thing, becoming a differentiator from the study of the application of problem-based learning models in thematic learning in elementary schools. So far, the implementation of character education in primary and secondary schools is carried out separately based on the subject of certain scientific materials. Studies on character based on scientific material subjects can be seen from a number of papers published in various reputable national journals and international journals.

Studies on character based on subject matter: are as follows (1) the subject of science matter, among others, conducted by Tutkun, E., Gorgut, I., & Erdemir, I. (2017); (2) the subject matter education: Hidayat, Abdul Rozak, Kembara, Parhan, (2022), Novianti, N. (2017); (3) the subject matter of mathematics science: Cahyaningsih, Ghufron, 2016; (4) the subjects matter of social humanities material: Meindl, P., Quirk, A., & Graham, J. (2018); (5) the subject of education and humanities materials: Revell, L., & Arthur (2007), Saidek, Islami, Abdoludin (2016), Ciampa, K., Wolfe, Z. M. (2021), Riyanto, Nandiyanto, Kurniawan, and Bilad (2022), Fahrannisa, A.L., Muktiarni, M., Mupita, J. (2022), Suhirman, 2020, Frisancho, S., & Delgado, G. E. (2018), Budiyo, 2021; (6) the subject matter education and language fields: Turan, F., & Ulutas, I. (2016); (7) the subject matter social and religious subjects: Anam, Degeng, Murtadho, Kuswandi (2019); (8) the educational material subjects: Bates, A. (2019); (9) the subject matter of language and humanities: Dempster, M. (2020); (10) the subject matter of Pancasila education and state citizenship: Dewi, Dantes, Yudiana, 2019; (11) the subject matter of science and agriculture Ismail and Oktadela, 2021.

From the study data and publications on these characters, it is revealed that there is no available information and studies on the application of certain learning models in elementary schools to develop character and life skills. From a psycho-pedagogical perspective, the success and achievement of cognitive, affective and psychomotor domain competencies is determined by the applied learning model (Wilson, 2013). Therefore, the study of the application of the character-laden learning model will determine the success, achievement and meaning in learning processes and activities.

In this paper, the significance of the problem-based learning model with character is measured from two dimensions, namely (1) the creative thinking ability proposed by Guilford, namely fluency of thinking, flexibility, elaboration and originality; (2) the dimensions of character developed by Lickona (1991) which include: caring, responsibility, creativity, hard work and honesty.

Referring to Dewey's (1964) view, these two dimensions of learning achievement can be realized with giving students the freedom to choose their own projects and learning activities and are carried out in small groups that allow them to interact and have dialogue. This is in accordance with the philosophy of problem-based learning models that promote collaborative, communicative, cooperative problem solving (Joyce, Well, and Calhoun, 2016). In this connection, Dick, Carey and Carey (2009:230) add that the meaningfulness of learning requires the role and presence of the teacher as a facilitator, mediator and motivator of learning for students.

In John Dewey's understanding (1964: 153), creative thinking skills and character dimensions can be realized when the school acts as a miniature community, namely an inquiry community that uses experience as learning foundation. For Dewey, education is a process of forming basic, intellectual and emotional skills in social life in society and interacting with the universe. The development of these basic skills is carried out

through inquiry which is the most effective problem solving method and contains cognitive, affective, and psychomotor dimensions.

In Dewey's understanding, inquiry is the basis as well as educational and learning processes and activities that contain experience, growth, experiment and transaction. Learning processes and activities that ignore inquiry as a sign of learning failure. Ignoring the ability and enthusiasm of students' inquiry has implications and places learning activities as figments, jokes and jokes (Lipman 1991: 15).

The use of problem-based learning model with character can be analyzed and linked to Vygotsky's theory of constructivism. The important concepts of Vygotsky's constructivism theory are the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) and scaffolding. Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) is the distance between the actual developmental level indicated by the ability to solve problems independently and the level of potential development, that is problem solving ability under adult guidance or by working with more capable peers.

The concept of the Zone of Proximal Development is related to Vygotsky's view, that knowledge is built through social interaction and becomes the basis for building further knowledge. The development of student knowledge is determined by two things: (1) knowledge that is constructed and carried out by students independently which is called actual knowledge. (2) potential knowledge in the form of knowledge or experience gained by students with the help of more mature people or competent peers. Actual knowledge is at the lower limit of the Zone of Proximal Development while potential knowledge is at the upper limit.

According to Vygotsky, so that actual knowledge and all student abilities develop and are at the upper zone limit, assistance and guidance called scaffolding provided by peers and/or teachers need to be gradually reduced in line with their level of physical and intellectual maturity. The help provided by the learner can be in the form of instructions, warnings, encouragement, describing the problem into other forms that allow students to be independent. In Vygotsky's understanding, two children who have the same actual level of development can have different levels of potential development. Each Zone of Proximal Development is different even though they are in similar learning situations (Jones & Thornton, 1993:20).

Based on the concept of the Zone of Proximal Development and scaffolding initiated by Vygotsky, in the learning process and activity, students are placed as active learners, student-centered instruction. In learning activities the teacher becomes a "guide on the side" by helping students find their own meaning, the teacher is not a "wise person on the stage who controls all learning activities. In accordance with the concept of the Zone of Proximal Development, the role of educators is as a mediator who encourages and bridges students in efforts to build their knowledge and competencies (Schunk (2012: 341).

The development of students' knowledge and their ability to solve various problems will develop when interacting with teachers and collaborating with peers. In relation to the ability to think creatively, critically and life skills and the ability to solve social problems, initially carried out and completed under the guidance and cooperation of others, after being internalized it can be done independently and independently. Students' knowledge of a social phenomenon, such as socio-cultural diversity, is initially below the zone of proximal development, after being internalized and developed independently into potential knowledge, the achievement is above the zone of proximal development.

In the context of learning socio-cultural diversity, Vygotsky's constructivism theory views that learning is meaningful when students can understand concepts, facts, socio-cultural processes through direct experience in society. Through social interaction with various social and ethnic groups at school and in the community, students will understand about social groups, ethnicity, diversity, society, social relations as concepts, facts, processes (Glaserfeld: 1989).

This shows that Vygotsky's theory of constructivism presupposes that students are subjects, active, creative, critical and characterized human beings who can construct knowledge through interaction with their social and cultural environment. The socio-cultural environment plays a major role in cognitive content, thinking skills and learner skills (Ormrod (2008: 57). Vygotsky's constructivism theory places cultural life and practice as an instrument in the cognitive development process, in the intermental and intramental fields. Cultural artifacts, social practices and language plays an important role in mediating students as learners and at the same time as members of the community and society.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

The conclusion of this research can be formulated as follows:

- (1) Problem-Based Learning Model Contained with Character resulting from this research is in the form of a learning set consisting of Teacher's Books, Student Handbooks, Socio-Cultural Diversity Modules, Learning Implementation Plans (RPP) and Student Worksheets (LKPD).
- (2) Based on the results of the validation carried out by 9 validators consisting of 3 validators in the field of material, 3 validators in the field of learning design and 3 validators in the language field, the Character-Based Problem-Based Learning Model consisting of five learning tools was declared valid with an average score of 3,76. The validity of the design aspects and learning media obtained an average score of 3.68, the

validity of the learning material aspects of 3.78; the design and media aspects have an average of 3.75 and the validity of the language aspects with an average value of 3.88.

- (3) The Problem-Based Learning Model that contains Character, which was developed after being tested on small groups, medium groups and large groups in elementary schools in Simalungan Regency and Pematang Siantar City, Sumatra Indonesia from the results of descriptive statistical analysis was declared effective for improving thinking skills, creative students. The effectiveness of the product model developed for small group is 73.95, standard deviation is 4.476, learning completeness is 55%. The effectiveness of the model product developed for medium group is 77.33, standard deviation is 2,592, learning completeness is 85% and the effectiveness of the model product developed for large group is 78,433, standard deviation is 3,061 and learning completeness is 76%. complete learning by 85%. The effectiveness of the developed model product was also proved from the increase in the acquisition of student learning outcomes between before and after the test and the difference in the average achievement of student learning outcomes between the experimental class and the control class.

4.2. Research Implication

The research implications are divided into theoretical implications and practical implications. The theoretical implications of the research are (1) from the data on the validity and effectiveness of the Character-Based Problem-Based Learning Model that was developed to strengthen the views expressed by Krathwohl (2002), Anderson & Krathwohl (2001), about factual, conceptual, procedural, and metacognitive knowledge, creative thinking and the critical and taxonomy of characters proposed by Lickona (1991). (2) From the data on the effectiveness of the problem-based learning model with character, it strengthens Dewey's (1964) view of students' thinking abilities.

In Dewey's understanding, creative abilities can be developed by giving students the freedom to choose their own projects and learning activities and providing space for interaction and dialogue. Dewey's view is in accordance with the philosophical foundation of the problem-based learning model which emphasizes collaborative, communicative, cooperative problem solving. Therefore, all school components should act as miniature inquiry communities that use experience as the basis for character building. Schools are required to develop life skills, cognitive, psychomotor and affective aspects of students in a balanced way by providing a space for dialogue and communicative social interaction.

The practical implications of developing a character- problem-based learning model are formulated as follows:

- (1) Improving students' creative thinking skills and character can be done by designing a systematic learning system that gives students the freedom to choose learning activities independently, providing space for dialogue and interaction and communication between students, between students and teachers and between students and the surrounding environment.
- (2) Actual knowledge and potential knowledge of students develop from the lower limit to the Zone of Proximal Development by placing teachers as facilitators and motivators, schools and the social environment as "engines" encouraging students to develop their abilities optimally.
- (3) In accordance with constructivism theory, learning processes and activities are said to be meaningful:
 - (1) when students can understand concepts, facts, social and cultural processes and life through direct experience in nature and in society
 - (2) students gain experience to know and solving social and scientific problems empirically through scaffolding.
- (4) Various natural phenomena, socio-cultural phenomena (such as socio-cultural diversity) and cultural artifacts are instruments to increase cognitive(creativity), affective and psychomotor development in the intermental and intramental fields.

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